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Presences and Arrivals in the Apulian Municipalities between 2013 and 2022

Tourism in the Bari area is growing. Otranto, Castellaneta and the Tremiti Islands lose tourists

The IPRES-Pugliese Institute for Economic and Social Research calculates the number of arrivals and presences in the Apulian municipalities between 2013 and 2022. Arrivals are considered as the number of Italian and foreign customers hosted in the accommodation establishments in the period considered. Overnight stays are indicated as the number of nights spent by Italian and foreign customers in hospitality establishments. The data relating to 177 Apulian municipalities will be considered below. Municipalities without a complete historical series have been omitted.

Ranking of municipalities by number of Italian arrivals. Vieste is in first place for the value of Italian arrivals in 2022 with an amount of 259441 units, followed by Bari with a value of 242728 units, Lecce with a value of 162230 units, San Giovanni Rotondo with a value of 151032, Ugento with a value of 103183, Otranto with an amount of 101326, Fasano with 100290, Gallipoli with 93289, Monopoli with 88472 units, Alberobello with an amount of 79045. In the middle of the ranking there are Massafra with a value of 3867 units, followed by San Vito dei Normanni with 3393, Ischitella with 3342, Putignano with 3270, Rutigliano with 3172, Cannole with 2912, Maruggio with 2777, Leverano with 2775, Palagiano with 2771, Patù with 2726, Diso with 2644. Minervino Murge closes the ranking with 217, Nociglia with 209, Lizzanello with 193, Aradeo with 118, Surbo with 115, San Michele Salentino with 98, Apricena with 78, Serracapriola with 77, San Cassiano with 66, Soletto with 44, Sanarica with 42.

Ranking of Apulian municipalities by value of Italian presences in 2022. Vieste is in first place for value of Italian presences with an amount of 1609847 units, followed by Ugento with 738852, by Peschici with 538195, Bari with 492691, Otranto with 475742, Carovigno with 448161, Gallipoli with 405015, Melendugno with 399902, Lecce with 397832, Fasano with 372377. In the middle of the table are Massafra with a value of 14724, followed by Crispiano with 13580, Molfetta with 13435, Giurdignano with 13283, Leverano with 12941, Mottola with 12028, Ceglie Messapica with 11601, Bitonto with 11458, Patù with 11194, Maruggio with 10912, San Vito dei Normanni with 10768, Palagiano with 10912, San Vito dei Normanni with 10768, Palagiano with 10379. Scorrano closes the ranking with 661, San Pietro Vernotico with 540, Ascoli Satriano with 528, Minervino Murge with 471, Surbo with 362, Aradeo with 289, Serracapriola with 225, Apricena with 219, Sanarica with 207, San Cassiano with 179, Soletto with 118.

Ranking of Apulian municipalities by value of Italian arrivals in 2022. Bari is in first place by value of Italian arrivals in 2022 with an amount of 206012 units, followed by Lecce with a value of 116898, by Vieste with a value of 70214, from Monopoli with 69127, Fasano with 65887, Polignano a Mare with 56748, Ostuni with 56700, Alberobello with 51271, Otranto with 48494, San Giovanni Rotondo with 38679. In the middle of the ranking there are Ortelle with an amount of 1016, followed by Lequile with 970, Morciano di Leuca with 958, Cavallino with 940, Alezio with 927, Gravina in

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Puglia with 921 units, Massafra with 889 units, Galatone with 888, Corsi with 871, Cassano delle Murge with 856, Grottaglie with 772. 66, Troia with 63, Aradeo with 57, Scorrano with 53, Deliceto with 27, Serracapriola with 24, Ascoli Satriano with 21, Apricena with 9, Soletto with 5, Sanarica with 3.

Ranking of the Apulian municipalities by value of the presence of foreigners in 2022. Bari is in first place for the value of the presence of foreigners in 2022 with an amount of 492665, followed by Vieste with 389922, by Fasano with 296130, Lecce with 288386, Monopoli with 232185, Ostuni with 189380, Polignano a Mare with 173256, Ugento with 169888, Otranto with 163620, Gallipoli with 142107. In the middle of the rankings are Zollino with 3611, Massafra with 3222, Canosa di Puglia with 3215, Capurso with 3177, Villa Castelli with 3156, Cerignola with 3119, Corsi with 3101, Leverano with 3042, Corigliano d'Otranto with 2975, Cavallino with 2961, Lizzano with 2907. Candela and Torremaggiore close the ranking with 177, Scorrano with 155, Troia with 134, Serracapriola with 96, Deliceto with 74, Ascoli Satriano with 62, Apricena with 31, Calimera with 24, Sanarica 11, Soletto with 5.

Ranking of Apulian municipalities by value of total arrivals in 2022. Bari is in first place by value of total arrivals with a value of 448740 units, followed by Vieste with an amount of 329655, Lecce with 279128, San Giovanni Rotondo 189711, Fasano with 166177, Monopoli with 157599, Otranto with 149820, Ostuni with 134554, Alberobello with 130316, Gallipoli with 129535. In the middle of the table are Massafra with 4756, Putignano with 4748, Leporano with 4726, Patù with 4500, Cagnano varano with 4342, Diso with 4304, Ischitella with 4000, Maruggio with 3795, Martano with 3649, Avetrana with 3644, Leverano with 3360. The ranking is closed by Sogliano Cavour with 321, Minervino Murge with 295, Scorrano with 283, Ascoli Satriano with 275, Calimera with 239, Surbo with 181, Aradeo with 175, Serracapriola with 101, Apricena with 87, Soletto with 49, Sanarica with 45.

Ranking of Apulian municipalities by value of total presences in 2022. Vieste is in first place by value of total presences in 2022 with an amount of 1999769, followed by Bari with an amount of 985356, Ugento with Ugento with 908740, Lecce with 686218, Fasano with 668507, Otranto with 639362, Peschici with 625454, Gallipoli with 547122, Carovigno with 538942, Ostuni with 517693. In the middle of the ranking we find Rutigliano with 13766, Cutrofiano with 13306, Canosa di Puglia with 12946, Mottola with 12885, Grottaglie with 12593, Palagiano with 12479, Alezio with 12084, Martano with 11944, Taviano with 11917, Putignano with 11305, Avetrana with 11246. Close the ranking San Pietro Vernotico with 949, Calimera with 870, Scorrano with 816, Minervino Murge with 689, Ascoli Satriano with 590, Surbo with 566, Aradeo with 497, Serracapriola with 321, Apricena with 250, Sanarica with 218, Soletto with 123.

Percentage variation of Italian arrivals in the Apulian municipalities between 2013 and 2022. Cellino San Marco is in first place by value of the percentage variation of Italian arrivals in the Apulian municipalities between 2013 and 2022 with a value equal to +911.68 or an amount equal to 6792, followed by Palo del Colle with an amount of 815.32% equal to 905 units, Arnesano with +678.38% equal to +251 units, Alezio with +673.95% equal to 1449, Biccari with 668.18% equal to 441 units, Salice Salentino Salice Salentino with 552.5% equal to 1326 units, Disco with +522.12% equal to 2219 units, Zollino with +489.57% equal to 563 units, Cassano delle Murge with 431.1% equal to 3923, and Acquaviva delle Fonti with 401.28% equal to 1252. Taranto is in the middle of the ranking with +25.30% equal to 13615 units, followed by Cavallino with +24.92% equal to 147 units, followed by Laterza with +24.14% equal to +98 units, Gallipoli with +24.14% equal to 17786 units, Castrignano del Capo with +22.79% equal to 3894 units, Ruvo di Puglia with +22.61% equal to 1516

units, Parabita with +22.35% equal to 156 units, San Severo with +21.58% equal to 2219 units, Monte Sant'Angelo with +21.13% equal to 2441 units, Carpino with +20.11% equal to 73 units, Ugento with +20.02% equal to 17211 units. The ranking closes with Troia with -59.97%, Casarano with -60.93% equal to -2498 units, Massafra with -61.08% equal to -6068 units, Poggiardo with -64.28% equal to -1771, Corigliano d'Otranto with -68.41 equal to -2118 units, Tuglie with -70.4% equal to -1139 units, Sanarica with -75.72% equal to -131, Apricena with -80.25% equal to -317 units, Soletto with -91.2% equal to -456 units, Trepuzzi with -94.57% equal to -8722 units, Lizzanello with -95.37 with -3972.

Winners and losers by value of the absolute change in Italian arrivals between 2013 and 2022. The winning countries by absolute change in the number of Italian arrivals between 2013 and 2022 are Vieste with 53696, Monopoli with 49162, Alberobello with 30538, Polignano a Mare with 26172, Fasano with 24611, Bari with 21587, with 24611, Bari with 21587, Carovigno with +19137, Trani with +18681, Melendugno with +18248, Gallipoli with +17786. Among the losers countries, i.e. the countries that have lost the most tourists, there are San Giovanni Rotondo with -29701 units, Castellaneta with -18502 units, Manfredonia with -18258 units, Vernole with -13299 units, Corato with -11535 units, Otranto with -9525 units, Lucera with -9311 units, Trepuzzi with -8722 units, Otranto with -9525 units, Lucera with -9311 units, Trepuzzi with -8722 units, Massafra with -6068 units, Tremiti Islands with -4773 units. We can note that the losers countries, with the exception of Corato, have important tourist facilities. The case of San Giovanni Rotondo is particularly serious, which highlights the crisis of religious tourism in Puglia, but also of Castellaneta which is a town with an important endowment of beaches. As well as Otranto which has lost about 9500 units, and also Lucera which has a significant historical-monumental heritage in the context of Frederick's Puglia. Finally, the case of the Tremiti Islands is even more serious. Between 2013 and 2022, the Tremiti Islands lost around 23.27% of Italian arrivals.

Winners and losers by value of total attendance in absolute value between 2013 and 2022. Bari is in first place for value of total attendance in absolute value between 2013 and 2022 with an amount equal to 433685 units or +78.61%, followed by Monopoli with 294522 units equal to +141.13%, Lecce with 229404 with +50.22%, Carovigno with 191925 equal to +55.31%, Polignano a Mare with +182898 equal to +133.68%, Fasano with +159446 units equal to +31.32%, Ostuni with 114909 equal to +28.53%, Valenzano with 109896 equal to +471.9%, Gallipoli with 96834 with +21.5%, Melendugno with 93268 +26.6%. Among the countries that are losers, i.e. countries that lost by number of total presences between 2013 and 2022, there are Peschici with -125787 equal to -16.74%, Otranto with -109329 units equal to -14.6%, Castellaneta with -100136 units equal to -24.57%, Manfredonia with -59641 units equal to -32.34%, San Giovanni Rotondo with -55.285 equal to -13.45%, Trepuzzi with -51573 equal to -92.3%, Casarano with -46414 equal to -89.72%, Taviano with -37817 equal to -76.04%, Tremiti Islands with -37411 equal to -40.28%, and Santa Cesarea Terme with -32710 equal to -29.31%. Also in this case, considering the total presences, i.e. both Italians and foreigners, it appears that many of the municipalities that have reduced the number of presences have important tourist and naturalistic infrastructure facilities such as for example Otranto, Peschici, Castellaneta, Tremiti Islands and Santa Cesarea Terme. Furthermore, the case of San Giovanni Rotondo is also very serious, highlighting the crisis of religious tourism in Puglia.

Ranking of Apulian municipalities by value of the change in total arrivals between 2013 and 2022. Bari is in first place by value of the change in total arrivals between 2013 and 2022 with a value equal to 151331 units equal to 50.88%. followed by Monopoli with 106483 units equal to +208.32%, Lecce with 75869 equal to 37.33%, Vieste with 74371 equal to +29.13%, Polignano a Mare with +72448 units equal to +166.09%, Fasano with +59,567 equal to +55.87%, Ostuni with +47,286 equal to

+54.18%, Gallipoli with +39,833 equal to +44.41%, Carovigno with +33,139 equal to +61.68%, Brindisi with +31,316 equal to +55.15%. We note that in percentage terms the countries that have grown the most in the top ten are Monopoli which doubled the total arrivals and Polignano a Mare which increased the value of arrivals by 166%. Among the countries that are losers there are Casarano with -4139 arrivals equal to -68.31%, Tremiti Islands with -4379 equal to -20.38%, Massafra with -6541 units equal to -57.9%, Trepuzzi with -8171 equal to -87.91%, Lucera with -9785 units equal to -43.16%, Corato with -11240 units equal to -45.16%, Vernole with -14243 equal to -47.09%, Manfredonia with -19609 units equal to -34.43%, Castellaneta with -26600 units equal to -34.95%, San Giovanni Rotondo with -27938 equal to -12.84%. However, overall between 2013 and 2022 the number of total arrivals increased by an amount equal to 1,055,473 units. However, it must be considered that of the 177 Apulian municipalities considered there are about 40 that have seen a reduction in the number of total arrivals. Therefore, the growth in the number of arrivals appears to be differentiated and concentrated above all in some municipalities regardless of the endowment of tourist structures and facilities.

Ranking of Apulian municipalities by value of the ratio between Presences/Arrivals in 2022. Below we present the ranking of Apulian municipalities by value of Presences/Arrivals which is a variable that offers an estimate of the number of nights that tourists stay in the municipalities. Leporano is in first place by value of the Attendance/Arrivals ratio in 2022 with an amount equal to 10.38 units, followed by Valenzano with 9.38, Ischitella with 8.51, Cagnano Varano with 7.54, Ugento with 7.26, San Michele Salentino with 7.21, Peschici with 6.91, Salve with 6.64, Vico del Gargano with 6.21 units. In the middle of the table is Taranto with 3.32, Sammichele di Bari with 3.29, Martano with 3.27, Andrano with 3.26, Torremaggiore with 3.25, Isole Tremiti with 3.24, Cursi with 3.22, Lizzano and Castro with 3.19, Serracapriola with 3.18. Trani closes the ranking with 1.99, Mottola with 1.97, Andria with 1.96, Bitonto with 1.92, Canosa di Puglia with 1.89, San Giovanni Rotondo with 1.88, Gravina in Puglia with 1.84, Alberobello with 1.82, Cassano delle Murge with 1.82, San Marco in Lamis with 1.77, Cellino san Marco with 1.25.

Conclusions. The number of tourists calculated in terms of both arrivals and overnights increased for the Apulian municipalities between 2013 and 2022. However, not all municipalities benefited from the growth in the number of both Italian and foreign tourists. There are some municipalities that have experienced a reduction in the number of tourists. In this sense, the conditions of Otranto, Peschici, the Tremiti Islands and Castellaneta are particularly serious. In this case there is certainly no shortage of naturalistic beauties, beaches and the possibility of welcoming tourists. The data show the lack of tourism economic policies that can also allow these municipalities to grow. Furthermore, religious tourism has also decreased in Puglia as demonstrated by the reduction of arrivals and attendances in San Giovanni Rotondo between 2013 and 2022. It is also necessary to create more connections between the municipalities that are growing and those that are losing tourists. For example, between Melendugno and Otranto there are about 30 km. Yet, Melendugno is growing in the number of tourists, while Otranto lost presences and arrivals between 2013 and 2023. In this sense, the Vieste-Peschici relationship should also be improved. The case of Castellaneta is difficult to explain. The municipality has lost almost 26,600 arrivals and about 100,000 presences despite the abundant supply of beaches. The result is therefore a difficulty in organizing tourist services in the Puglia region, which has a much lower performance than it could have by increasing investments, at least in countries that certainly have significant beach facilities. Finally, we note that the tourist who arrives in Puglia generally stays for 2-3 days. Probably one of the reasons that led to the low stay of tourists is the lack of adequate investments in the hotel and hospitality sector. In fact, the decision to focus on bed and breakfasts, widespread hotels, and impromptu allocations, however valuable, in

farms renovated with public funds, has ended up reducing the stay of tourists. Obviously, with the permanence, the possibility of creating tourist services that can generate greater added value for the Apulian economy is also reduced. It is therefore necessary to activate the following policies:

- Invest in coastal Apulian municipalities that have beaches to stimulate tourist entrepreneurship, promote investments in structures, increase the offer of services and commercial activities for tourists;
- Promote religious tourism in Puglia starting from San Giovanni Rotondo and also offering integrated itineraries with other municipalities that have important religious traditions;
- Invest in the construction of hotels, residences, tourist villages to increase the offer and lengthen the stay of tourists in Puglia;
- Create promotion programs for tourism entrepreneurship from a managerial, investment and qualified human capital point of view, focusing on the well-being and quality of the tourist experience.

Finally, it is necessary to distinguish between occasional tourism entrepreneurs and professional tourism entrepreneurs. Renting out a room on the internet does not generate entrepreneurial human capital in the tourism sector. It is necessary to make serious investments, which are based on the formation of human capital, also opening to foreign capital. Furthermore, entrepreneurs and public institutions need to invest in the quality of tourism and not in luxury. Because in the end the luxury market is not accessible for Puglia. The rich go where there are other rich people. And it is highly unlikely that a rich person would give up the Côte d'Azur, Sardinia or Forte dei Marmi, to go to Southern Italy, to a region, Puglia, where the per capita income is around 15,000 euros, a value that risks becoming low even by Eastern European standards. You won't find the billionaire on the cruise that lands in Bari, nor among those who go to Gallipoli to party. We therefore need a more serious mentality of the Apulian public and private ruling class involved in tourism, to prevent the important opportunity represented by the sector from becoming speculation or, worse, a joke compared to regions and places that instead invest hundreds of millions euros and offer thousands of jobs, perhaps offering quality and discretion. Those who do strategic management know that the opportunity for tourism in the future may not always be open. In fact, we do not know what could happen with the new tourist investments in the eastern Adriatic and in Turkey, or in North Africa. Indeed, while the Apulian economy is struggling to take off, other areas of the Mediterranean have higher growth rates and invest in tourism in a very competitive way.

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Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Presenze Stranieri, Arrivi Totali, Presenze Totali 2022

Comune	Presenze Stranieri	Comune	Arrivi Totali	Comune	Presenze Totali
Bari	492665	Bari	448740	Vieste	1999769
Vieste	389922	Vieste	329655	Bari	985356
Fasano	296130	Lecce	279128	Ugento	908740
Lecce	288386	San Giovanni Rotondo	189711	Lecce	686218
Monopoli	232185	Fasano	166177	Fasano	668507
Ostuni	189380	Monopoli	157599	Otranto	639362
Polignano a Mare	173256	Otranto	149820	Peschici	625454
Ugento	169888	Ostuni	134554	Gallipoli	547122
Otranto	163620	Alberobello	130316	Carovigno	538942
Gallipoli	142107	Gallipoli	129535	Ostuni	517693

Variazione Percentuale delle Presenze Totali e Notti per Turista

Arrivi italiani, presenze italiane, arrivi stranieri 2022

Rank	Comune	Arrivi Italiani	Comune	Presenze Italiane	Comune	Arrivi Stranieri
1	Vieste	259441	Vieste	1609847	Bari	206012
2	Bari	242728	Ugento	738852	Lecce	116898
3	Lecce	162230	Peschici	538195	Vieste	70214
4	San Giovanni Rotondo	151032	Bari	492691	Monopoli	69127
5	Ugento	103183	Otranto	475742	Fasano	65887
6	Otranto	101326	Carovigno	448161	Polignano a Mare	56748
7	Fasano	100290	Gallipoli	405015	Ostuni	56700
8	Gallipoli	93289	Melendugno	399902	Alberobello	51271
9	Monopoli	88472	Lecce	397832	Otranto	48494
10	Alberobello	79045	Fasano	372377	San Giovanni Rotondo	38679